

A Data Pipeline for Digital Humanities

Development of a Solution for Humanities Data Digitization

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Summary. The dissertation project focuses on humanities data and humanities researchers that have not been involved in the Digital Humanities, and the proposal of a solution to enable them to prepare their data for digital sharing. In doing so, the poster presents a process beginning with an exploration of the traditional data space, continues with the determination of a target group, which will lead to the formulation of requirements in accordance with the software engineering process. Furthermore, the exploration of existing digital open data tools and platforms will serve to determine technical requirements of a data pipeline solution designed for the target audience and their data.

1 Introduction

As a result of ethically relevant considerations and long-standing legal restrictions, the digital collection and preservation of research data in the humanities is far behind that of digital data and computational methodologies in the natural sciences^{1,2}. At the same time, as early as 2012 Fiormonte warned against the domination of a small group of privately funded researchers dominating the field and proposed an inclusive, diverse model of DH³, an idea that has also been supported by others^{4,5}. This creates a pressure to make data available within public infrastructure. Since 2012, how far has the provision of humanities data progressed? Is it possible to determine common issues in different marginalized humanities research that hinder digitization of data? And if so, what would a solution look like to facilitate the digitization of humanities data that has not been made available thus far?

¹ cp. Collins et al, "Going Digital," 10.

² cp. Rehbein, *On Ethical Issues*, 631-654.

³ Fiormonte, *Towards a Cultural Critique*, 59.

⁴ cp. Collins et al, "Going Digital," 10.

⁵ Wuttke, *Wege bereiten*, 1-16.

2 Developing a Digital Humanities Pipeline

The presented project proposal follows several steps with the final goal of creating a pipeline for humanities researchers to contribute to existing and future public federated data publication services.

2.1 Exploration of the Humanities Data Space

In a first step, an exploration of the humanities data space shall determine the low hanging fruit of data that has not been made available as research data according to its technical, legal, and ethical characteristics. It is likely, but not necessary that data belonging to this group is used by a group of researchers representing a heterogeneous cross-section of humanities research fields⁶.

In a second step, specific non-functional qualitative requirements are determined based on the needs assessments carried out thus far in the Humanities.^{7,8,9}

2.2 Exploration of the Public Federated Data Platforms and Tools

In a third step, the technical functional requirements¹⁰ of existing public federated data services and tools will be determined. In this analysis, the focus will be on those tools that follow technical paradigms and are supported by existing national (NFDI) and European (EOSC) initiatives, such as the DARIAH-DE collection registry in order to warrant future application.^{11,12,13,14,15}

2.3 Development of a Data Pipeline for Digital Humanities

The initial non-functional requirements are specified further in an iterative user-centric software design and development process^{16,17} incorporating functional requirements. Finally, the aim is to develop a

⁶ cp. Collins et al, "Going Digital," 10.

⁷ Imeri and Danciu 2017, p. 10.

⁸ Schopfel and Prost 2016, p. 100.

⁹ ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148, *Requirements Engineering*, 43.

¹⁰ *ibid.*, 13.

¹¹ Rfll, *Föderierte Dateninfrastrukturen*, 42.

¹² cp. Gradl et al, *Heterogene Daten*, 1-10.

¹³ cp. Patrick 2023.

¹⁴ cp. Herklotz et al. 2021.

¹⁵ cp. Strathern et al. 2020.

¹⁶ Bednar and Welch 2008, 225-236.

¹⁷ Raven and Flanders 1996, 1-13.

platform for researchers to participate in open science with shared open data. All the steps that will serve in the development of the pipeline shall be presented through the poster, as a basis for discussion.

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